

Somerville, MA December 10th 2024

**Small Group (SG) of the Methodological Panel (MP) of the
Clean Development Mechanism (CDM)
United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)**

Dear Members,

In March 2023, leveraging our decade-long expertise in assessing the environmental impacts of woodfuel harvesting [e.g. 1, 2-4], we were contracted by the UNFCCC to estimate national and subnational values for the fraction of Non-Renewable Biomass (fNRB) across much of the Global South. After several interactions with the MP, which required of certain adjustments to the methodology, we submitted our [final report](#) on June 20 2024. On December 10, 2024, we upgraded the results on the analysis [web platform](#), extending projections to 2050 (previously limited to 2030) and replacing standard deviations with standard errors for improved clarity.

In this letter, we do not delve into the methodological details or results already outlined in the full report or available on the model's web platform. Instead, we aim to provide our expert opinion on why and how cookstove project developers should adopt these new values. Importantly, we argue against allowing developers to generate their own estimates using alternative tools.

Sincerely yours,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'A. Ghilardi', written over a horizontal line.

Dr. Adrian Ghilardi
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A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'Robert Bailis', written over a horizontal line.

Dr. Robert Bailis
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Tool 30 must be discontinued if rampant over-crediting wants to be ameliorated

Accurately assessing the environmental impacts of woodfuel harvesting is undoubtedly complex, but challenging inflated fNRB values is straightforward.

Here’s why:

1. Applying the currently registered fNRB values (from Verra, Gold Standard, and CDM) to 2010 woodfuel demand maps results in rates of aboveground biomass depletion so rapid that they conflict with all available datasets on forest and woodland distribution by 2020. For some countries, these estimates imply a completely tree-less landscape well before 2020—an assertion that is plainly meaningless (Figure 1).
2. Comparing all observable biomass losses from deforestation and degradation—caused by agriculture, selective logging, altered fire regimes, grazing, urbanization, road construction, and other drivers—against woodfuel demand reveals a stark reality. For many countries, fNRB values are significantly lower than those found in the registries; meaning the true fNRB values must be at the most equal than these maximum thresholds. Yet, these inflated figures have been generating credits for years (Figure 2).

The implications are severe: these credits are used by companies to offset actual emissions, creating a false sense of progress while the climate crisis worsens. By perpetuating this flawed system, the damage to global climate mitigation efforts is immense.

Figure 1: The vast majority of fNRB values in the registries of the Voluntary Carbon Market would result in a rapid depletion of all aboveground biomass.

Source: [5]

Figure 2: Comparison of aboveground biomass losses by all causes between 2010 and 2022 across selected countries, alongside total woodfuel demand (in wood equivalent units) for the same period.

Notes to Figure 2: Interestingly, the new fNRB values at 1km resolution are, in some cases, significantly higher than observed losses. This phenomenon is addressed in a subsequent section: “The new fNRB estimates will significantly reduce over-crediting, while the risk of under-crediting remains minimal.” You can access this tool in [MoFuSS’s main webpage](#), under Tools: “Observed fNRB – Beta”.

The new fnr estimates seem to be closer to reality than any previous estimates

Accurately assessing the environmental impacts of woodfuel harvesting remains challenging, as determining the extent to which observed degradation can be attributed to specific drivers is inherently complex. Unlike deforestation caused by agriculture, fires, or infrastructure, woodfuel harvesting often leaves no distinct, discernible patterns on the landscape. While validating the new fNRB estimates within a statistical framework is feasible, it requires resources and effort far beyond the funding and timeline provided by the UNFCCC for this study. A brief overview of our ongoing research in this area is provided under “Future Research Directions.”

So, how can we be confident that the new fNRB values are more realistic than the Tool30-derived estimates? First, as outlined earlier, the current values reported by project developers are demonstrably inconsistent with aboveground biomass (AGB) dynamics. Second, our new simulations align closely with observed changes in specific regions, as shown in Figure 3. Importantly, this comparison extends beyond fNRB values to include the spatial distribution of simulated versus observed AGB changes—a significant advancement toward high-integrity fNRB assessments. To date, no project developer in any registry within the Voluntary Carbon Market has provided even minimal validation—spatial or otherwise—of their fNRB values. This underscores the progress achieved in our approach, which represents a major step forward in addressing this critical gap. Third, the new fNRB estimates align with the ranges observed in our previous assessment for 2009 [1], which, while based on a simpler approach, shared key underlying features, such as spatially explicit patterns of supply and demand.

Figure 3. Spatial comparison between observed and simulated dynamics in aboveground biomass between 2010 and 2020.

Notes to Figure 3: We are presenting here just one of 30 comparison sites in Malawi and Mozambique. In all cases, the difference in fNRB was never greater than 15%. However, differences in spatial patterns highlight the need for further calibration. While many more analyses are required for this type of validation (e.g. attribution remains a challenge), it's worth acknowledging the significant improvement in these results compared to those from Tool30, which rely solely on spreadsheet calculations as evidence, with no cross-checking whatsoever against any independent dataset.

The new fNRB estimates will significantly reduce over-crediting, while the risk of under-crediting remains minimal.

The 1km analysis tends to overestimate woodfuel-driven aboveground biomass (AGB) losses (i.e., NRB and fNRB) for five key reasons. As a result, using mean values as a default will mitigate over-crediting but not eliminate it entirely. The relative importance of each factor will vary by region, highlighting the need for context-specific assessments.

1.- Non-energy anthropic pressure

The non-energy anthropic pressure in MoFuSS comprises a set of parameters designed to calibrate the natural regrowth potential of forests and woodlands, accounting for non-energy drivers of forest degradation. These drivers include selective logging for timber and pulp, extensive grazing, altered fire regimes, edge effects, and more [6, 7]. The 1km model assumes that these non-energy drivers are prevalent everywhere, implying that even if all woodfuel demand were eliminated, woodlands would not fully regrow to their biophysical potential due to the ongoing pressure from an unknown mix of non-energy anthropic activities.

As MoFuSS simulations progress, woodfuel harvest reduces aboveground biomass (AGB) stocks during the analysis period, with natural regrowth occurring, based in part on the spatial intensity and temporal trajectories of harvest and collection events. In many parts of the world where AGB stocks are below their biophysical potential and gains are scattered, this assumption seems valid. However, there are numerous regions where AGB gains are widespread and even have outpaced losses over the past two decades [8]. When running high-resolution versions of MoFuSS over specific areas with significantly more AGB gains than losses, and calibrating the non-energy anthropic pressure accordingly, fNRB simulations show a significant drop compared to global results.

2.- Resolution

The AGB map used in the global analysis [9] fails to account for all woody resources utilized for fuelwood and charcoal, mostly in arid or highly degraded areas such as Haiti [4]. When running high-resolution versions of MoFuSS using 30m to 100m AGB maps in arid or degraded regions, there is more biomass available compared to the 1km version, with a drop in fNRB values [10].¹ These high-resolution maps are currently a bottleneck for running MoFuSS at 100m as they are not freely available and can be quite expensive from private providers. So far, we have used selected areas of high-resolution, multitemporal AGB maps to calibrate and validate MoFuSS between 2010 and 2022. The comparison with the 1km estimates shows lower fNRB values.

¹ Note that ecosystems with higher-than-previously-estimated carbon levels result in more credits for conservation and restoration projects. However, the opposite is true for cookstove projects; as more carbon is stored per areal unit, the impact is diminished due to inelastic demand.

3.- Deforestation

Many areas around the world are experiencing deforestation due to non-energy drivers, resulting in land use and cover changes [e.g. 11]. When there is demand for woodfuel, the wood from land clearing operations is often used as fuelwood or for making charcoal. Occasionally, using this wood as fuel can be seen as a catalyst of change rather than the underlying driver, as the profits from selling charcoal or fuelwood can finance the land clearing for conversion to cropland or grazing areas. In any case, we couldn't model this on a global scale due to site-specific circumstances governing these patterns. When the "deforestation submodule" is activated in MoFuSS and calibrated to simulate land clearing events into the future, fNRB values tend to decrease because a tunable percentage of the felled wood is assumed to be used as fuelwood and/or converted into charcoal depending on their demand trends.

4.- Elasticity in demand scenarios

We assume woodfuel demand scenarios are inelastic, which is rarely accurate. In situations of acute scarcity, driven for example by the expansion of land clearing operations or by tightening enforcement on woodfuel access, production, or trade, people simply use less wood and switch to lower forms of biomass such as crop straws [12]. It is worth noting that inelastic demand can also underestimate fNRB values in woodlands with higher-than-previously-estimated AGB. MoFuSS has yet to incorporate elasticity of demand, not due to modeling challenges, but because of the significant lack of information on the subject. A first indicator could be the correlation between unitary woodfuel usage and availability at the landscape level [13].

5.- Carbon accumulation potential from natural regrowth

MoFuSS uses IPCC default values [14] to derive the intrinsic growth rate of AGB for various ecosystems and ecological zones. It has been published that these rates "may underestimate aboveground carbon accumulation rates by 32 per cent on average and do not capture eight-fold variation within ecozones" [15]. An essential aspect of the ongoing calibration and validation efforts, as briefly mentioned earlier, involves adjusting regrowth parameters using observed datasets.

Woodfuel harvesting occurring within Protected Areas could underestimate fNRB values

The global model estimates that woodfuel harvested within protected areas is about 10% of the expected harvest without protection, predominantly near the boundaries. However, discussions with project developers reveal that in areas with weak enforcement, people enter deeper into protected zones for fuelwood and charcoal production, effectively ignoring protections. The porosity of protected areas is one of many parameters in MoFuSS and should be adjusted in regions with insufficient enforcement. When protected areas are mostly surrounded by low-AGB density supply zones such as croplands or rangelands, and their porosity is increased, the fNRB tends to be higher.

In conclusion, a higher-resolution version of MoFuSS, specifically parameterized for a given site and calibrated with independent data on AGB dynamics, could potentially yield significantly lower fNRB values in the baseline compared to the global 1km results. This hypothesis can only be confirmed through further analyses in selected case studies across the Global South.

The new fNRB estimates are perfectible, but they are certainly way less flawed than the figures reported by project developers in the registries

Due to funding and time constraints, our modeling approach could not integrate several features. For instance, we were unable to calibrate land-use change dynamics for every country, incorporate the latest pixel-based regrowth potential data, or validate results with high-resolution simulations over selected areas of interest. These and other limitations are detailed extensively in the report.

Notwithstanding these challenges, efforts to address some of these shortcomings are underway. Two manuscripts, scheduled for submission in 2025, will present refinements to the modeling approach and key findings. However, improving our methodology will not result in radically different outcomes—certainly not the exaggerated figures submitted by project developers, who have garnered inflated credits across all three main registries (Verra, Gold Standard, and CDM) for almost two decades [16, 17].

In the medium to long term, we are pursuing several research directions. Some of these initiatives are expected to yield results by mid-2025, while others may require the following year to achieve significant progress:

1. Prospective Land Use and Cover Simulations: Beyond Deforestation

We are expanding our focus to include prospective scenarios that go beyond forest loss and gain driven by non-energy factors. This includes analyzing the sensitivity of our results to various land-use and land-cover trajectories, offering a more nuanced understanding of their impacts.

2. The “Marginal” Approach

Wood-saving technologies deployed at scale across space and time are unlikely to influence fNRB values uniformly. In some areas, reductions in woody biomass consumption may initially have a high impact on non-renewable biomass (NRB), with diminishing effects over time. Conversely, other regions might experience the opposite trend, where impacts grow more pronounced over the course of the intervention. Understanding these variations is crucial for designing effective and equitable strategies.

3. Expanding Beyond fNRB and AMS.II.G

The modeling approach developed for this study moves beyond existing methodologies, such as AMS.II.G, offering a more versatile and comprehensive framework. By incorporating information on both past and future deployment of woodfuel-saving devices, the model estimates CO_{2e} emissions reductions by comparing aboveground biomass (AGB) losses and gains under two scenarios: Business-as-Usual (BAU) and demand-reduction. Pixel-level differences in AGB dynamics between these scenarios represent the avoided emissions attributable to the intervention, removing the need for fNRB calculations or aggregation by administrative boundaries. This approach will also enable successful projects to assess an alternative no-cookstove scenario, a feature frequently requested by established project developers. Additionally, this methodology has broader applications, including identifying regions where interventions would have the greatest impact on reducing non-renewable biomass (NRB).

4. Validation of simulations in the period 2010-2022

As noted earlier, validating the new fNRB estimates is possible but comes with significant constraints. When comparing simulated versus observed changes during a past period (2010–2022) at 1km resolution, it is difficult to pinpoint the primary drivers behind the observed changes, relying instead on anecdotal evidence or expert opinions. Nevertheless, observed changes serve as an upper bound for the simulations—our model cannot simulate more degradation than what is observed, as that would simply be incorrect. Another limitation is that the most practical results from our approach are for future

periods, such as 2020–2050 or 2020–2030, which cannot be validated directly. Instead, we must trust that prospective simulations are robust, based on their alignment with observed changes during past periods.

Next year, we plan to explore a completely new methodology that focuses on charcoal production—a significant driver of tree cover loss, particularly in certain ecosystems like drylands. This approach, achievable only at 100m resolution, involves identifying kiln scars and estimating the volume of wood used, which can then be compared to biomass losses in surrounding areas [18]. While this method, a decade in development, is not feasible at a global scale or 1km resolution, it holds promise for targeted hotspots. However, it requires considerable human effort when applied over large areas; for instance, covering a country the size of Kenya would take approximately 6–8 months.

Final Recommendation to the MP²

1. Project developers must utilize the tool available at <https://www.mofuss.unam.mx/mofuss-ds/> to obtain either the mean values provided, or results derived from uploading or delineating their specific project area within the tool.
2. Developers should not rely on self-generated estimates (including those obtained through external consultants).

When we published our first global assessment in 2015 and 2017 [1, 2], the UNFCCC gave project developers two options: to either use our default values or derive their own using Tool30. The outcome, after all these years, is telling—virtually no project developers made the effort to evaluate whether their estimates bore any plausible connection to reality. The truth is simple: project developers, registries, or brokers cannot produce credible values because they lack impartiality. A trusted, independent third-party source is the only path forward.

We argue that the fNRB estimates we have produced are far closer to reality than every estimate registered by Verra, Gold Standard, or the CDM. This discrepancy has led to massive over crediting since 2006, undermining the integrity of the cookstove projects in the Voluntary Carbon Market.

Now, for the second time, the UNFCCC faces the decision of recommending default fNRB values. Don't repeat the mistakes of the past. This time, the level of scrutiny and the number of scientists committed to safeguarding the credibility of the Voluntary Carbon Market are significantly greater. Continuing to allow project developers to use inflated fNRB values will do far more harm than good in the long term. This heightened scrutiny is causing major companies to become increasingly cautious about greenwashing [19], and developers are now more conscious that fraudulent activities carry real consequences^{3 4}.

² A very similar recommendation was also submitted as a [public comment during the first round](#), by a renowned Professor of the University of California, Berkeley, specialized in Public Policy and carbon crediting.

³ <https://www.justice.gov/usao-sdny/pr/us-attorney-announces-criminal-charges-multi-year-fraud-scheme-market-carbon-credits>

⁴ <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2024/oct/04/ex-carbon-offsetting-boss-kenneth-newcombe-charged-in-new-york-with-multimillion-dollar>

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